

BARYON AND LEPTON CONSERVATION

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A. Baryon Conservation

Until recently all theories of elementary particles assumed the absolute validity of the law of baryon conservation i.e. the number of baryons plus antibaryons is constant in any interaction. In its earliest form the principle was discussed by Stückelberg⁽¹⁾ and Wigner⁽²⁾ as a conservation law for nucleons. Now with the developing hope for a unified theory of electromagnetic, weak and strong interactions it may be that nucleon conservation is approximate.⁽³⁾ Unfortunately current theories provide little quantitative guidance to the experimentalist with nucleon lifetime predictions ranging over many orders of magnitude most of which are, and will very likely remain, beyond the range of experimental test. This matter of experimental test can be put into perspective by taking 10^{36} as an upper limit on the number of nucleons that can be observed i.e. 10^6 tons. A nucleon lifetime of 10^{36} years would produce only one decay per year, a signal which would require for its observation the identification of backgrounds from atmospheric neutrino interactions. Since we are now at a lifetime $> 2 \times 10^{30}$ years it therefore appears that there remains a range $< 10^5$ to be investigated.

In considering experimental tests of baryon conservation we observe that within the realm of known elementary particles, violation of this conservation law cannot occur without the associated violation of at least one of the conservation laws of energy-momentum, spin, charge, or lepton number. It is clear that a wide variety of experimental tests can be made depending on the associated violations assumed. However two general features are noted: baryon decay can be signaled by observation of a decay product, or de-excitation of the resultant nucleus,⁽⁴⁾ or both. A most attractive possibility in principle which is least dependent on detailed assumptions as to the decay mode is the deuteron decay

In this example, decay of the proton into unspecified products could be signaled by a low energy gamma ray from capture of the sister neutron. The limit set by Jenkins and Dix for this reaction is $> 3 \times 10^{23}$ yrs.⁽⁵⁾ However, because of the background at low energies it is unlikely that this approach can be pushed to the limits already reached by the search for products of decays obeying more restrictive conditions. Since it appears that lepton conservation is the least well founded of the conservation laws, most of the experimental tests have been based on searches for charged products including leptons. Table I summarizes experimental results to date.

The most stringent limit for a decay including at least one muon or a π^+ (which then decays) was obtained by searching for muon decays in a 20 ton detector located deep underground and is $> 2 \times 10^{30}$ yrs. (6) In actual fact 5 such events were seen during the few year run. These events were concluded to arise either from the production of low energy stopping muons by the interaction of atmospheric neutrinos in the detector and surrounding rock or from nucleon decay. Muons produced in the atmosphere, penetrating the rock and then decaying in the vicinity of the detector are estimated to give rise to $< \frac{1}{10}$ the observed rate. Although ν produced muons could account for most or all of the observed events the rate predicted from this source is sufficiently uncertain that it is not possible to rule out completely, nucleon decay as a source of muons which decayed in the detector.

The data from which these results were deduced were obtained incidental to the deep underground atmospheric neutrino experiment of the Case-Wits-Irvine group. The large area (180m^2) thin slab detector of that experiment was ill suited to a determination of the muon and electron energies. In addition the overall detection efficiency was only $\sim \frac{1}{3}$. Since the energy spectrum, for the muons from nucleon decay is expected to differ markedly from that of a neutrino produced muon* this lack of energy resolution was a serious deficiency. A much improved experiment

*Multiparticle decays such as suggested by Pati and Salam ($p \rightarrow 3\nu + \pi^+$, $p \rightarrow 4\nu + \mu^+$) would yield an upper limit for muon energy of < 200 MeV.

capable of more precise determination of the pion or muon and decay electron energies is under consideration by W. R. Kropp and the author. In this version a large (~ 200 tons) segmented liquid scintillation detector located in a deep (1950 feet) salt mine and enclosed in a cosmic ray anti-coincidence would be scanned for decays having first pulse energies less than a few hundred MeV. Such a detector is anticipated to be capable of detecting a half life $\leq 10^{32}$ years.

As indicated, the ultimate limit on the detection of nucleon decay is set by the background due to muons from atmospheric neutrinos. In the event that there exist nucleon decay modes from which more than one muon results, a much more distinctive signal is produced and schemes can be envisioned which use very large volume water cerenkov detectors to see the sequence of pulses produced by the muons followed by decay electrons.

B. Lepton Conservation

Though no violation of either has been observed, lepton conservation⁽⁷⁾ is much less well founded than baryon conservation. A most sensitive test of lepton conservation for charged weak currents is provided by the absence of neutrinoless emission in double beta decay:

a second order process which can occur when the first order beta decay is forbidden either by energetic considerations or by a large nuclear spin change.

An excellent candidate for double beta decay experiments is ^{82}Se recently determined by geochemical means⁽⁸⁾ to have a half life for decay to ^{82}Kr of $2.8 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{20}$ yrs. (Srinivasan et. al.).

A lower limit of 3.1×10^{21} yrs. has been set on the neutrinoless mode by Wu and Cleveland⁽⁹⁾ who searched for a peak from a Se sample containing 26.5 gm of ^{82}Se .

This represents a limit on the branching ratio to the neutrinoless mode of 9%. Taking into account the relative phase space $\sim 10^{-6}$ for the modes with and without neutrino emission the amplitude of the lepton violating coupling is seen to be $\leq 3 \times 10^{-4}$.

This result is based on the presence of geochemical evidence for $\beta\beta$ decay and absence of a lepton violating term. Moe and Lowenthal⁽¹⁰⁾ are engaged in an experiment employing 15 gms of ^{82}Se on very thin foils (7 mg/cm^2) in a cloud chamber with the goal of observing double beta decay accompanied by $2\bar{\nu}_e$. The continuous spectrum expected in this case is much more difficult to discriminate against background than is the line sum spectrum of the no neutrino mode. Such a direct observation of double beta decay would be very reassuring and would provide a more detailed test of the theory for the lepton conserving case.

TABLE I. Summary of nucleon half-life experiments*

Experimenters	Nucleon half-life (yr)	Nucleon decay detection method	Nucleon source
Goldhaber (1954) (unpublished)	$>1.4 \times 10^{18}$	Spontaneous fission of Th^{232} after excitation by nucleon decay. Assumes that the rearrangement energy upon loss of a nucleon is sufficient to cause fission of the residual nucleus.	
Reines, Cowan, and Goldhaber (1954)	$>1 \times 10^{22}$	High-energy decay fragment. Liquid scintillation, 30 m below surface	Toluene in detector and surrounding detector
Reines, Cowan, and Kruse (1957)	$>4 \times 10^{23}$	Proton decay in deuteron. High-energy fragment plus neutron left over from deuteron after decay of proton. Delayed coincidence and liquid scintillation 61 m below surface.	
Backenstoss, Frauenfelder, Hyams, Koester, and Marin (1960)	$>2.8 \times 10^{26}$	High-energy fragment; upward going particles. Čerenkov and scintillation 800 m below surface. At least 250 MeV assumed to be available to decay particle. Result based on combined measurements for neutrons and protons.	Water, lead, and rock.
Giamati and Reines (1962)	$>1 \times 10^{26}$ to $>7 \times 10^{27}$ to depending on mode.	High-energy fragment. Liquid scintillation with anticoincidence shield, 585 m below surface.	Decalin in detector and surrounding iron.
Kropp and Reines (1964)	$>6 \times 10^{27}$ to $>4 \times 10^{28}$ to depending on mode.	High-energy fragment. Liquid scintillation with anticoincidence shield, 585 m below surface.	Decalin in detector and surrounding iron.
Dix and Jenkins (1970) (unpublished)	$>2 \times 10^{23}$	Neutron left over from deuteron after decay of proton. Not dependent on decay mode.	Heavy water in Čerenkov detector.
Gurr et. al. (1967)	$>2 \times 10^{28}$ to $>8 \times 10^{29}$ to depending on mode.	High-energy fragment. Liquid scintillation, 3200 m below surface. Horizontally going particles.	Surrounding rock, mineral oil scintillator, and detector box.
Reines and Crouch (1974)	$>2 \times 10^{30}$	Decaying muon. Liquid scintillation, 3200 m below surface.	Surrounding rock, mineral oil, scintillation, and detector box.

*For references to 1967 see H. S. Gurr, W. R. Kropp, F. Reines and B. S. Meyer, Phys. Rev. 158, 13 (1967).

References and Footnotes

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Pati, Salam, and Smith discuss the possibility of baryon decay with the production of leptons on the assumption the "quarks" carry integral electric charge, and that conservation of fermion number $F (= B + L)$ replaces separate baryon (B) and lepton (L) number conservation. They suggest that the decay of "quarks" though allowed in this model by electric charge conservation is greatly inhibited by the associated multiple change of baryon number.

Predictions of the nucleon half life for such decays are extremely sensitive to the model chosen, ranging from $\sim 10^{15} \rightarrow 10^{75}$ yrs. (Smith).

Giorgi and others preferring a different point of view suggest that an extended gauge group with fractionally charged quarks which can unify strong, weak, and electromagnetic interactions also implies a failure of baryon conservation. He estimates a proton lifetime which may lie in the general vicinity of $\sim 10^{32}$ yrs.

4.) S. P. Rosen, Phys. Rev. Lett. 34, 774 (1975) has suggested a geochemical method in which one would search for ^{38}Ar produced in old potassium ores by the decay of ^{39}K . As Rosen points out, if one assumes that proton decay can occur without breaking up the daughter ^{38}Ar and there are no other ways of generating ^{38}Ar , such an approach would be sensitive to limits $\sim 10^{31-2}$ years.

M. Goldhaber has observed, Proc. Am. Phil Soc. 119, 24 (1975), that data (1958) of G. N. Flerov on spontaneous fission enables a limit for nucleon decay to be set $> 10^{23}$ yrs.

5.) Private communication, T. L. Jenkins (unpublished Ph.D. thesis F. Dix, Case Western Reserve University, 1970).

6.) F. Reines and M. F. Crouch, Phys. Rev. Lett. 32, 493 (1974).

[Ya. B. Zeldovitch and L. B. Okun preprint No 39 (1975) Inst. of Applied Math. Ac. Sci U.S.S.R discuss cosmological consequences of baryon non-conservation.

- 7.) Excellent review articles dealing with the subject of lepton conservation have been written by Fiorini and by Rosen: E. Fiorini, *Il Nuovo Cimento* 2, 1 (1972), S. P. Rosen, Chapter 5, *Proceedings Neutrino-1974*, Am. Inst. of Phys.
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